

RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship – Data Stewardship Landscape Report Resource Matrix

RDA Supporting Output

DOI: 10.15497/RDA00077

Authors: Lorna Wildgaard, Jukka Rantasaari

Published: 4 October 2022

Version: 1.0

Abstract: This dataset includes the resources which were included in the Research Data Alliance Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group (RDA PDS-IG) Training Landscape sub-group report published in October 2022. The literature was structured into the following categories: data stewardship; education and training of data stewards; RDM education; training materials; data management plan templates; documents about the skills needed to support EOSC and FAIR principles; data management in the humanities, industry, life sciences, natural sciences, public institutions and the social sciences. The aim was to identify papers concerning the RDM needs of researchers and data stewards and their role in the RDM life cycle. The screening resulted in 125 papers that are used as the knowledge base for the output report.

Impact: The resource database will give information to all who are interested in developing their data stewardship skills needed to better serve the needs of researchers.

Language: English

License: [Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

RDA webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/professionalising-data-stewardship-ig>

Citation and Download:

<i>resource</i>	<i>provider</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>internet link</i>
23 Things: Libraries for Research Data	RDA Libraries for Research Data IG	dx.doi.org/10.15497/RDA00005	
5 models for data stewardship (A SAS best practices white paper by Dyché & Polsky)			https://www.sas.com/content/dam/SAS/en_au/doc/whitepaper1/5%20Models%20Data%20Stewardship%20White%20Paper.pdf
A beginner's guide to data stewardship and data sharing (Dijkers, 2019)	Spinal Cord (journal)	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41393-018-0232-6	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41393-018-0232-6
A conceptual enterprise framework for managing scientific data stewardship	Data Science Journal	http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2018-015	https://datascience.codata.org/article/10.5334/dsj-2018-015/
A day in the life of a Data Steward (Kees den Heijer)	Delft University of Technology		https://librarianresources.taylorandfrancis.com/a-day-in-the-life-of-a-data-steward/
A design framework and exemplar metrics for FAIRness (Wilkinson et al., 2017)	Scientific Data	https://doi.org/10.1101/225490	
A focus on... the emerging role of 'Data Steward' in Ireland	DRI		https://dri.ie/blog-data-stewardship
A global perspective on evolving bioinformatics and data science training needs	Briefing in Bioinformatics 20(2)	10.1093/bib/bbx100	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28968751/
A Multi-Institutional Project to Develop Discipline-Specific Data Literacy Instruction for Graduate Students Part of the Curriculum and Instruction Commons, Educational Assessment, Evaluation, and Research Commons, and the Other Education Commons Recommen	Purdue e-pubs		https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1011&context=lib_fspres
A Pilot Competency Matrix for Data Management Skills: A Step toward the Development of Systematic Data Information Literacy Programs	Journal of eScience Librarianship		https://escholarship.umassmed.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1096&context=jeslib
Advancing Research Data Management in the Social Sciences: Implementing Instruction for Education Graduate Students Into a Doctoral Curriculum (Thielen, 2017)	Behavioral and Social Sciences Librarian	https://doi.org/10.1080/01639269.2017.1387739	https://doi.org/10.1080/01639269.2017.1387739
Advancing the Framework: Use of Health Data—A Report	Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association	10.1197/jamia.M2905	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2585531/
An Educational Program on Data Curation	Graduate School of Library and Information Science University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign		1. https://www.ideals.illinois.edu/handle/2142/3493 / 2. https://www.ideals.illinois.edu/bitstream/handle/2142/3493/ALA_STS_poster_2007.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y
An Innovative Government Architecture with Semantic Technology	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN THE DIGITAL AGE	10.4018/IJPADA.2016040104	
Analytics stewardship and the community of practice (Palmer, 2014)	IBM Data Magazine		https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84906075501&origin=inward&txGid=fe4798da10446570c5d3b96944e3498b
ARGOS DMP Tool	OpenAIRE / EUDAT		https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/index.html

<i>resource</i>	<i>provider</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>internet link</i>
Arts and Humanities Research Council Data Management Plan Rubric (Donaldson & Higman, 2018)	Zenodo	54296<53-irshs5;89976	
At the watershed: Preparing for research data management and stewardship at the University of Minnesota Libraries	Johns Hopkins University Press and the Graduate School of Library and Information Science. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign		https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1256&context=libraryscience
Become a Data Steward: Step-by-Step Career Guide			https://study.com/articles/Become_a_Data_Steward_Step-by-Step_Career_Guide.html
Big data and the evolving role of governance (Soares, 2013)	IBM Data Magazine		https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84894415988&origin=inward&txGid=f9c86e715c39abb49842a6712f1d6a74
Bioinformatic training needs at a health sciences campus (Oliver, 2017)	PLoS ONE	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0179581	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0179581
Building digital workforce capacity and skills for data-intens	OECD	https://doi.org/10.1787/23074957	https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/e08aa3bb-en.pdf?expires=1629107029&id=id&accname=quest&checksum=02381A71B592973B0FD37B0B4E7F06EB
Business and IT roles for improving data resource quality (Brackett, 2003)	Cutter IT Journal		https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-0345870981&origin=inward&txGid=7ff2d45d30b2adaef5365ce5ca82a43
Business intelligence as a competitive differentiator (Bogza & Zaharie, 2008)	2008 IEEE International Con	https://doi.org/10.1109/AQTR.2008.458874	
Carpentries-based workshop: FAIR data and software (2018)	Software Carpentry Foundation		https://tibhannover.github.io/2018-07-09-FAIR-Data-and-Software/
Certified Data Steward (CDS) Program	eLearningCurve		https://ecm.elearningcurve.com/Certified_Data_Steward_Program_CDS_s/136.htm
CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide training toolkit	CESSDA		https://www.masterdata.co.za/index.php/cds/data-stewardship-training# https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/source/43
Cloudy, increasingly FAIR; revisiting the FAIR Data guiding			https://content.iospress.com/download/information-services-and-use/isu824?id=information-services-and-use%2Fisu824
Collibra Data Steward Learning Path	Information Services & Use Collibra University		https://university.collibra.com/learn/public/learning_plan/view/46/collibra-data-steward-learning-path
Compliance Insurance for Data Integrity: An Information Governance Plan Should be on Your New Year's Resolution List.	Journal of Health Care Compliance		https://web-a-ebsscohost.com.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/ehost/detail/detail?vid=0&sid=1f6501c3-4403-4600-a139-b3ccca46d10a%40sdc-v-sessmgr03&bdata=JnNpdGU9ZWlhvc3QtbGl2ZQ%3d%3d#AN=99924397&db=bth
Conference (2019): Data Steward education - coordination or competition?	DeiC (Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation)		https://www.deic.dk/da/datamanagement/data-steward-event

<i>resource</i>	<i>provider</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>internet link</i>
Corporate data quality management from theory to practice (Lucas, 2010)	IEEE		https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5556606
Course: Implementation of Data Management Plans & Data Cross-disciplinary Higher Education of Data Science – Beyond the Computer Science Student	ELIXIR-SI IOS Press		https://elixir.mf.uni-lj.si/course/view.php?id=40 https://content.iospress.com/articles/data-science/ds005
D&H data is collected not generated. Collection methods may incur hidden bias. -- Difference between raw and analysed data more blurred.-- Data publication environment is new, A&H follow older book and article publishing patterns.	Danish National Forum for Research Data Management		https://zenodo.org/record/3609516#.X1XIJ8gzY2w
D7.2: Interim report and catalogue of EOSC skills training and educational materials (Kuhn & Streit, 2017)	EOSC pilot		https://eoscipilot.eu/sites/default/files/eoscipilot-d7.2_0.pdf
DARIAH Pathfinder to Data Management Best Practices in the Humanities			https://campus.dariah.eu/resource/dariah-pathfinder-to-data-management-best-practices-in-the-humanities
Data analysis & stewardship	Helis Academy		https://helisacademy.com/en/data-analysis-stewardship
Data Analytics - DAT (Canisius)	Canisius		https://catalog.canisius.edu/graduate/courses/dat/
Data anonymisation training toolkit	The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit		https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/topics/data-anonymisation
Data Business Plans and Governance Programs Aligning Transportation Data to Agency Strategic Objectives (Stickel & Vandervalk, 2014)	Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board	https://doi.org/10.3141/2460-17	
Data Curation Network: A Cross-Institutional Staffing Model for Curating Research Data	International Journal of Digital Curation		https://experts.umn.edu/en/publications/data-curation-network-a-cross-institutional-staffing-model-for-cu
Data files for National Coordination of Data Steward Education in Denmark: Final report to the National Forum for Research Data Management (DM Forum) (Wildgaard et al., 2020)		https://doi.org/10.5081/zenodo.3634756	
Data Governance & Data Steward Certification (2015)	Dataversity		https://www.slideshare.net/Dataversity/data-governance-data-steward-certification
DATA GOVERNANCE CHALLENGES FACING CONTROLLERS (Rickards & Ritsert, 2012)	International Journal of Business, Accounting, and Finance		https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339713098_Data_Governance_Challenges_Facing_Controllers/link/5e60d141a6fdc cbeba1ca6c5/download
Data governance creating value from information assets (Bhansali, 2013)	Taylor & Francis		https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054649077&doi=10.1201%2fb15034&origin=inward&txGid=7b51529074f0866f4b8560f82dbb890b
Data Intelligence Journal	The MIT press	https://www.mitpressjournals.org/loi/dint	https://www.mitpressjournals.org/loi/dint
Data management challenges in analysis and synthesis in the ecosystem sciences (Specht et al., 2015)	Science of the Total Environment	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.03.092	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.03.092
Data Management Plans for Humanities and Social Sciences	Compute Canada HSS Series		https://hss-series.netlify.app/dmp/

<i>resource</i>	<i>provider</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>internet link</i>
Data management plans: the missing perspective	Journal of Biomedical Informatics		https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1532046417300990
Data Science as a Service	International Journal on Advances in Software		https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Svetlana_Gerbel/publication/341234847_Data_Science_as_a_Service_-_Prototyping_an_integrated_and_consolidated_IT_infrastructure_combining_enterprise_self-service_platform_and_reproducible_research_In_International_Journal_On_Advances_in_So/links/5f07115fa6fdcc4ca459b678/Data-Science-as-a-Service-Prototyping-an-integrated-and-consolidated-IT-infrastructure-combining-enterprise-self-service-platform-and-reproducible-research-In-International-Journal-On-Advances-in-So.pdf
Data science in data librarianship: Core competencies of a data librarian (Semeler, Pinto, & Rozados, 2019)	Journal of Librarianship and Information Science	https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000617742465	https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000617742465
Data Stewards Interest Group	DTL (NL)		https://www.dtls.nl/community/interest-groups/data-stewards-interest-group/
Data Stewards to the rescue, please!	CSC, DeiC, SURF		https://www.inthefieldstories.net/data-stewards-to-the-rescue-please/
Data Stewardship Competence Centers (DSCC)		https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/dscc/	https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/dscc/ https://www.routledge.com/Data-Stewardship-for-Open-Science-Implementing-FAIR-Principles/Mons/p/book/978103209570710.5281/zenodo.2669150
Data Stewardship for Open Science	CRC press		
Data stewardship on the map: A study on tasks and roles in Dutch research institutes	Icldm Data Stewardship Task Group		
Data Stewardship Training	DTL-Learning / ELIXIR-NL Learning		https://www.dtls.nl/training-and-education/data-related-training/
Data Stewardship Wizard	DSW		https://ds-wizard.org/
Data Stewardship: Addressing Disciplinary Data Management Needs (Teperek et al., 2018)	International Journal of Digital Data Curation	https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v13i1.604	https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v13i1.604
Data Stewardship: An Actionable Guide to Effective Data Management and Data Governance (Plotkin, 2014)			https://www.sciencedirect.com/book/9780124103894/data-stewardship
Datatree - Data Training Engaging End-users	Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)		https://datatree.org.uk/course/
Dealing with third party data coming from cultural heritage institutions	SSHOC DARIAH		https://zenodo.org/record/4518889#.YDyU7GhKiM9
Defining data librarianship: a survey of competencies, skills, and training (Federer, 2018)	Journal of the Medical Library Association	https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2018.306	https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2018.306
Determining Data Information Literacy Needs: A Study of Students and Research Faculty (Carlson et al, 2011)	Purdue e-pubs		https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1031&context=lib_fsdocs
Digital competencies – urgently needed! – Recommendations on career and training prospects for the scientific labour market.	Rat für Informationsstrukturen		http://rfii.de/download/digital-competencies-urgently-needed-october-2019/

resource	provider	DOI	internet link
Digital cultural heritage as humanities data: a labs approach	Ghent University		https://www.slideshare.net/schambers3/digital-cultural-heritage-as-humanities-data-a-labs-approach
Digital skills forFAIR and openscience	EU		https://www.eifl.net/system/files/resources/202102/ki0221054enn.en_.pdf
Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research	Open Book Publishers		https://www.openbookpublishers.com/product/1108
Disciplinary differences in faculty research data management practices and perspectives (Akers & Doty, 2013)	International Journal of Digital Curation	https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v8i2.263	https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v8i2.263
Do researchers use open research data? Exploring the relationships between usage trends and metadata quality across scientific disciplines from the Figshare case	Journal of Information Science	10.1177/0165551520961048	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0165551520961048
Doctoral Students' Educational Needs in Research Data Management: Engaging Researchers with Data Management: The Cookbook	International Journal of Digital Curation Open Book Publishers	https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v16i1.684	https://www.openbookpublishers.com/product/1080
EOSC pilot: D7.1: Skills landscape analysis and competence model (Whyte & Ashley, 2017)	EOSC pilot		https://eoscipilot.eu/content/d71-skills-landscape-analysis-and-competence-model
EOSC pilot: D7.3 Skills and Capability Framework	European Open Science Cloude for Research Pilot Project		https://eoscipilot.eu/sites/default/files/eoscipilot-d7.3.pdf
EXPERIENCE: Succeeding at Data Management—BigCo Attempts to Leverage Data (Aiken, 2016)	Journal of Data and Information Quality	https://doi.org/10.1145/2893482	
Exploring research data management planning challenges in practice (Lefebvre et al., 2020)	IT - Information Technology	https://doi.org/10.1515/itit-2019-0029	https://doi.org/10.1515/itit-2019-0029
Factors influencing the data sharing behavior of researchers in sociology and political science (Zenk-Möltgen et al., 2018)	Journal of Documentation	https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-09-2017-0126	https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-09-2017-0126
Fading Away... The challenge of sustainability in digital studies	digital humanities quarterly		http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/14/3/000484/000484.htm
FAIR data stewardship: Supporting FAIR data interoperability			https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/events/fair-data-stewardship-supporting-fair-data-interoperability/
FAIR enough? Building DH Resources in an Unequal World	Humanities Commons		https://hcommons.org/deposits/item/hc:32187/
FAIR for Beginners	DeIC		https://vidensportal.deic.dk/en/FAIR
FAIR from the perspective of the Humanities V2.pptx			https://figshare.com/articles/presentation/FAIR_from_the_perspective_of_the_Humanities_V2_pptx/8342585
FAIR Science for Social Machines: Let's Share Metadata	MIT Data Intelligence		https://direct.mit.edu/dint/article/1/1/22/9976/FAIR-Science-for-Social-Machines-Let-s-Share
FAIRsFAIR Focus Group: University of Amsterdam FAIRsFAIR	FAIRsFAIR		https://www.fairsfair.eu/articles-publications/fairsfair-focus-group-university-amsterdam
FAIRsharing as a community approach to standards, repositories and metadata	Nature		https://www.nature.com/articles/s41587-019-0080-8

resource	provider	DOI	internet link
Final report: Towards FAIR data steward as profession for ZonMw the lifesciences. Report of a ZonMw funded collaborative approach built on existing expertise		10.5281/zenodo.3474789	
Finnish DMP evaluation guidance (Tuuli working group, 2021)	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.354296	
Foundations of Data Stewardship (Smith)	EW Solutions		https://www.ewsolutions.com/foundations-data-stewardship/
GDPR & Ethical Issues with Social Media Data			https://zenodo.org/record/4558694#.YDyVZGhKiM9
Getting the Central RDM Message Across: A Case Study of Central versus Discipline-Specific Research Data Services (RDS) at the University of Cambridge (Castle, 2019)	Libri	https://doi.org/10.1515/libri-2018-0064	https://doi.org/10.1515/libri-2018-0064
Governance over critical data elements	IBM Data Manag. Mag.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84900445236&partnerID=40&md5=6c09b8708f8cdb417c881d070b7ce6da
Helis Academy - Data analysis & data stewardship	Helis Academy		https://helisacademy.com/en/data-analysis-stewardship
Heritage Data Reuse Charter Information and developments around the Heritage Reuse Charter	DARIAH		https://datacharter.hypotheses.org/
HOW RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT CAN CONTRIBUTE TO EFFICIENT AND RELIABLE SCIENCE (Lefebvre, Schermerhorn, & Spruit, 2018)	26th European Conference on Information Systems: Beyond Digitization - Facets of Socio-Technical Change, ECIS 2018		https://dspace.library.uu.nl/bitstream/handle/1874/371758/1260_doc.pdf?sequence=1
How to identify and assess Research Data Management (RDM) costs (based on the guidelines of the UK Data Service and the Landelijk Coördinatiepunt Research Data Management)	OpenAIRE		https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-to-h2020-mandates-rdm-costs
In Aggregate: Trends, Needs, and Opportunities from Research Data Management Surveys (Goben & Griffin, 2019)	College and Research Libraries	https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.80.7.903	https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.80.7.903
Information Culture and Data Stewardship	University of Pittsburgh		https://www.icds.pitt.edu/degree-programs/master-of-library-and-information-science-online/mlisonline/
Institutional Readiness for Data Stewardship: Findings and Recommendations from the Research Data Assessment	Georgia Tech Library Annual Reports		https://smartech.gatech.edu/bitstream/handle/1853/48188/Research%20Data%20Assessment%20Final%20Report.pdf?sequence=4&isAllowed=y
Introduction to the Course Data Science essentials. Part 1 and Part 2. From Open Data to Open Innovation (Sempreviva, 2019)	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3580532	
Invest 5% of research funds in ensuring data are reusable (Mons, 2020)	Nature	https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00505-7	
Issues in Biomedical Research Data Management and Analysis: Needs and Barriers (Anderson et al., 2007)	Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0178261	https://doi.org/10.1197/jamia.M2114
LEGO® Metadata for Reproducibility game pack	University of Glasgow		http://eprints.gla.ac.uk/196477/

<i>resource</i>	<i>provider</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>internet link</i>
LERU Doctoral Summer School on Data Stewardship 08.07.2016	LERU		https://www.leru.org/news/leru-doctoral-summer-school-on-data-stewardship
LIBER Open Science Training Methods and Practices Across European Research Libraries - Survey Analysis	LIBER		https://zenodo.org/record/3903142
Library space assessment~ a professional education case study.	Performance Measurement & Metrics		https://www-emerald-com.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/insight/content/doi/10.1108/PMM-05-2017-0015/full/html
LibSmart course	University of Edinburgh		https://www.ed.ac.uk/information-services/help-consultancy/rm-and-consultancy/academic-support-librarians/libsmart
Life sciences data steward function matrix (Scholtens et al., 2019)	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2561723	
Measuring Data Management Practice Maturity: A Community's Self-Assessment (Aiken et al., 2007)	Computer	https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2007.139	
Metadata 4 machines help you find and (re)use relevant research data (metadata for machines (M4M) workshop in Leiden, Hettne & Verhaar, 2018)	GoFAIR Leiden together with the Research Data Alliance		https://digitalscholarship.leiden.nl/articles/metadata-4-machines-help-you-find-and-reuse-relevant-research-data
National Coordination of Data Steward Education in Denmark: Final report to the National Forum for Research Data Management (DM Forum) (Wildgaard et al., 2020)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3609516	
National Open Research Landscape (draft) Report	NORF		https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BF22CA_OIQCOTFvOzC676QYd8-6PjY2h4faBKt1OPd4/edit
Open a GLAM Lab: Digital Cultural Heritage Innovation Labs	Digital Cultural Heritage Innovation Labs, Book Sprint		https://glamlabs.pubpub.org/
Open Data for Humanists, A Pragmatic Guide (Edmond & Tóth-Czifra, 2018)			https://zenodo.org/record/2657248#.YVQijmYzaCc
Open Data, Grey Data, and Stewardship~ Universities at the Privacy Frontier	Berkeley Technology Law Journal		https://arxiv.org/abs/1802.02953
Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Centu	National Academy of Sciences		https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK525410/#sec_000138
Parthenos data management plan template - draft			https://www.rd-alliance.org/sites/default/files/attachment/PARTHENOS%20DM_draft.pdf
Planning to meet the costs of managing research data to be FAIR (Whyte et al., 2021)	FAIRsFAIR	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4518900	
Populating the Data Ark: An attempt to retrieve, preserve, and liberate data from the most highly-cited psychology and psychiatry articles (Hardwicke & Ioannides, 2018)	PLOS One	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0201856	
Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship	NPOS-F	10.5281/zenodo.4623713	

<i>resource</i>	<i>provider</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>internet link</i>
Professionalising data stewardship: Dutch projects (ZonMw, NPOS-F) (Jetten et al., PROMPTINGAN EOSC INPRACTICE			https://zenodo.org/communities/nl-ds-pd-ls?page=1&size=20
Reframing Data Stewardship Education in Denmark and abroad (Wildgaard, 2020)	EU	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3628374	https://publications.europa.eu/en/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/5253a1af-ee10-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1
Research Data Management and the Canadian Academic Library: An Organizational Consideration of Data Management and Data Stewardship	Partnership: The Canadian Journal of Library and Information Practice and Research		https://journal.lib.uoguelph.ca/index.php/perj/article/view/2990/3278
Research data management at London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine: Web survey report (Knight, 2013)			http://blogs.lshrm.ac.uk/rdmss/files/2013/04/LSHTM-RDM-Web-Survey-Report.pdf
Research Data Management Competencies Self-Assessm	Boise State University	https://doi.org/10.18122/dataservices.8.boisestate	
Research data management in academic institutions: A scoping review (Perrier et al., 2017)	PLoS ONE		https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0178261
Research data management in practice: Results from a cross-sectional survey of health and medical researchers from an academic institution in Australia (Krahe et al., 2020)	Health Information Management Journal	https://doi.org/10.1177/1833358319831318	https://doi.org/10.1177/1833358319831318
Scientific Stewardship in the Open Data and Big Data Era — Roles and Responsibilities of Stewards and Other Major Product Stakeholders (Peng et al., 2016)	D-Lib Magazine	https://doi.org/10.1045/may2016-peng	
Stewardship of Research Data			https://smartech.gatech.edu/bitstream/handle/1853/42091/STI-C-dataCuration.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y https://hal.inria.fr/hal-01562860
Survey on researchers requirements and practices towards Cultural Heritage institutions	HAL-INRIA		
Teaching (FAIR) data management and stewardship	19 NOV 2019 FOCUS GROUP UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM AMSTERDAM, NETHERLANDS		https://www.eua.eu/events/106-teaching-fair-data-management-and-stewardship.html
The 2014 DAF Survey at the University of Sheffield (Cox & Williamson, 2015)	International Journal of Digital Curation	https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v10i1.362	https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v10i1.362
The FAIR guiding principles for data stewardship: fair enou	Nature		https://www.nature.com/articles/s41431-018-0160-0#Sec11
The medical library association data services competency: A framework for data science and open science skills development (Federer et al., 2020)	Journal of the Medical Library Association	https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2020.909	https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2020.909
The Objectives, Scope and Activities of aPossible GO TRAIN ImplementationNetwork (Hodson et al., 2017)	CODATA	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1168503	
The risk of losing thick description: Data managementchall Hal	Archives-ouvertes.fr	alshs-02115505	https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-02115505/document

<i>resource</i>	<i>provider</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>internet link</i>
The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit	SSHOC project partners DANS, LIBER, CLARIN, UKDA, GESIS, UCL and OEAW.		https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/entities?search=&f%5B0%5D=collectons%3ATraining%20Discovery%20Toolkit&f%5B1%5D=content_type%3Asource
The State of Assessing Data Stewardship Maturity – An Overview	Data Science Journal		https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2018-007/
The views, perspectives, and experiences of academic researchers with data sharing and reuse: A meta-synthesis (Perrier, Blondal, & MacDonald, 2020)	PLoS ONE	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229182	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229182
Time to Professionalise Data Stewardship (Cruz et al., 2019)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3420178	
Towards a community-endorsed data steward profession d	Zon-MW	10.5281/zenodo.2554973	https://zenodo.org/record/2554974#.YLn3x6HTX4Y
Training	SSHOC		https://sshopencloud.eu/training
Training for Data Stewards (2017)	4TU.ResearchData & TU Delft Library		https://openworking.wordpress.com/2017/09/18/training-for-data-stewards/
TURNING FAIR INTO REALITY	EU		https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf
Understanding methodological and disciplinary differences in the data practices of academic researchers	Library HiTech		https://www.emerald-com.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/insight/content/doi/10.1108/LHT-02-2014-0021/full/html
Understanding methodological and disciplinary differences in the data practices of academic researchers (Weller & Monroe-Gulick, 2014)	Library Hi Tech	https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-02-2014-0021	https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-02-2014-0021
User needs assessment for research data services in a research university	Journal of Librarianship and Information Science		https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0961000619856073
User needs assessment for research data services in a research university (Joo & Peters, 2019)	Journal of Librarianship and Information Science	https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000619856073	https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000619856073
Visions and Challenges in Managing and Preserving Data to Measure Quality of Life (Estrada-Galinares & Wac, 2018)	IEEE	10.1109/FAS-W.2018.00031	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8599538
What Do We Know about the Stewardship Gap (York, Gutmann, & Berman, 2018)		https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2018-019	